

In vivo antidepressant activity of *Cecropia reticulata*

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Received 8 May 2026 ♦ Accepted 13 May 2026 ♦ Published 29 May 2026

Citation: Marinov L, Dakovska A, Momekov G, Rivera-Mondragón A, Ionkova I, Zarev Y (2026) In vivo antidepressant activity of *Cecropia reticulata*. Pharmacia 73: e198967. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e198967>

Abstract

The genus *Cecropia* (Urticaceae) is of increasing scientific interest due to its diverse phytochemical profile and potential therapeutic applications. This study aimed to evaluate the antidepressant-like activity of *Cecropia reticulata* leaf extract *in vivo* using the forced swimming test in mice. The lyophilized extract was obtained by ultrasonic extraction with 70% methanol. Behavioral parameters, including activity and immobility time, were evaluated following acute (5-day) and chronic (10-day) administration at doses of 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg, using VisionEngine, an artificial intelligence-based software for precise quantification of active and inactive periods. The results revealed a dose-dependent, non-linear effect. The most significant antidepressant-like activity was observed at the dose of 250 mg/kg after short-term administration. Double or even higher doses (1000 mg/kg) demonstrated inconsistent or reduced effects after long-term treatments. These results indicate that a methanolic extract of *C. reticulata* exhibits moderate antidepressant activity, possibly mediated indirectly by phenolic and terpenoid derivatives, which are commonly reported metabolites in the genus *Cecropia*. Further studies are essential to identify the active compounds and clarify the underlying mechanism of action.

Keywords

Cecropia reticulata, antidepressant activity, forced swimming test, medicinal plants

Introduction

Major depressive disorder, also known as depression, is a common mental illness that significantly affects daily life and quality of life. It is a global health burden characterized by a persistent low mood, loss of interest, and loss of pleasure in usual activities. An estimated 332 million people worldwide suffer from depression according to recent epidemiological data. Depression is approximately 1.5 times more prevalent in women than in men. Globally,

more than 10% of pregnant and postpartum women suffer from severe depressive disorders. In 2021, an estimated 727,000 people lost their lives due to suicide. It is the third leading cause of death for people aged 15–29 (Anon 2026). The specific neurochemical mechanism of depression has not yet been identified, although scientific studies suggest that oxidative stress factors cause psychiatric disorders (Lu et al. 2022; Ming and Kan 2024). Since oxidative stress contributes to cell damage and death, when brain cells are exposed to chronic stress factors, this often leads to

behavioral and biochemical dysfunctions. Current common antidepressant therapies, including tricyclic antidepressants such as imipramine, amitriptyline, doxepin, and others, have a significant effect but are often associated with side effects such as cardiac toxicity, sexual dysfunction, body weight gain, sleep disorders, and delayed therapeutic effects. This has led to increased interest during the last decade in plant-derived compounds with potential antidepressant properties (Juszczak et al. 2021). The phytochemical compounds in plants are constantly being explored through various experimental studies to determine the molecular basis of how medicinal plants work in relation to drugs and diseases and to develop nutraceuticals for improving conditions. Based on the compounds with antidepressant-like activity found in plants, various antidepressant screening models can be used, such as the tail suspension test, forced swimming test, chronic unpredictable stress test, sucrose preference test, monoamine oxidase inhibition assay, learned helplessness test, open field test, and hole board test (Martins and S 2018). The antidepressant potential of natural products has been extensively investigated; for instance, methanolic and hydroalcoholic extracts of *Acorus calamus* L. rhizome have shown significant activity (Yousuf et al. 2020), crude extracts of Peruvian *Hypericum* spp. exhibited antidepressant-like activity (Ccana-Capatinta et al. 2014), and the ethanolic extract of areca nut (50 mg/kg, p.o.) demonstrated antidepressant-like activity, evidenced by reduced immobility time in both the acute forced swimming test and tail suspension test (Bende et al. 2016). The genus *Cecropia* (Urticaceae) comprises 66 species distributed in Central America and is widely used in traditional medicine for cardiovascular, metabolic, and respiratory disorders. Phytochemical studies of the plant indicate the presence of terpenes, flavonoids, proanthocyanidins, and phenolic acids, which exhibit antioxidant and neuroprotective properties (Dajas et al. 2003). Some of the best-known and most extensively studied species of the genus *Cecropia*—*C. angustifolia*, *C. glaziovii*, and *C. pachystachya*—have been reported to contain flavonoids, phenolic acids, and terpenoids, which are widely believed to exert anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects (Costa et al. 2011; Khan et al. 2018; Rivera-Mondragón et al. 2021; Al Shammari 2024; Mesquita et al. 2026). The limited depth of existing phytochemical and pharmacological research on the genus *Cecropia* highlights the need for further investigation, particularly regarding the previously unstudied species *C. reticulata* (Hilty 1980; Rivera-Mondragón et al. 2021).

In the current study, *Cecropia reticulata* Cuatrec. was investigated for antidepressant activity using the forced swimming test. The limited studies of this species, combined with its widespread ethnomedicinal use, define the leaf extract of *C. reticulata* as a suitable candidate for *in vivo* evaluation of the potential antidepressant activity of the plant. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the antidepressant activity of a *C. reticulata* extract in experimental mice using a well-established preclinical model, specifically the forced swimming test (Porsolt et al. 1977).

This will be achieved by assessing behavioral outcomes indicative of antidepressant effects, followed by statistical analysis and advanced data processing using machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) approaches to interpret the obtained results.

Materials and methods

Plant material and extraction

The taxonomic classification was carried out by the botanist Orlando O. Ortiz. The plant material was subsequently deposited in the Herbarium of the University of Panama (voucher number 3225 OO). Pre-dried and powdered leaves of *C. reticulata* (660 g) were extracted using ultrasound-assisted extraction with 70% methanol (8 L). The resulting total extract was concentrated on a vacuum evaporator and lyophilized, stored in a cool, dry, and dark environment (*C. reticulata* total extract, CRTE). Prior to the experiment, the extract was suspended in 0.5% aqueous sodium carboxymethyl cellulose solution.

Experimental design

A total of 40 male albino mice with body weights approximately 25–30 g were obtained from the National Breeding Center, Sofia, Bulgaria. The mice were housed in Plexiglas cages (one per cage) in a 12/12 light/dark cycle under standard laboratory conditions (ambient temperature 20 ± 2 °C and humidity 72 ± 4 %) with free access to water and standard pellet mice food. The animals acclimatized for 10 days in the vivarium of the Faculty of Pharmacy of the Medical University of Sofia. All performed procedures were approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (449/10.10.2025).

The forced swimming test is a widely used method for testing depressive states during which experimental mice or rats are forced to swim in a transparent cylinder filled with water, and their behavior is studied and measured over time. When put in the water, mice show existential behaviors, such as rapid swimming or attempts to climb the wall, which show a response to stress. When treated with antidepressants, rodents show increased mobility and escape behaviors (Porsolt et al. 1977). The experimental animals were randomly divided into eight test groups of five mice each ($n = 5$ per group) for acute (5-day treatment) and chronic (10-day treatment) evaluation. The animals were administered treatments via oral gavage. Group 1 served as the control and received 0.5% aqueous sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (1.5 mL/100 g body weight/day). Groups 2, 3, and 4 were treated with *C. reticulata* total extract (CRTE) at doses of 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg bw/day, respectively, for 5 days. On day 5, the animals were evaluated using the forced swimming test, during which periods of activity and immobility were recorded over a total duration of 4 min (from the 2nd until the 6th min of the experiment). For the chronic evaluation of CRTE activity,

the same experimental design and doses were applied over a 10-day treatment period (Groups 5, 6, and 7). Group 8 served as the positive control and received the antidepressant imipramine at a dose of 15 mg/kg body weight via oral gavage, administered as a single dose 1 h prior to the test. The test was recorded, and the video was processed using VisionEngine, an artificial intelligence-based program allowing accurate measurement of the active and inactive periods during the experiment.

Data analysis

The results were processed and analyzed with the help of the nonparametric Mann–Whitney *U* test with a confidence interval of 95%. Differences were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Effects compared with the negative (untreated) control after 5-day treatment

On the fifth day of the experiment, clear differences were observed between the negative control group and the group receiving 250 mg/kg of substance. The results of the Mann–Whitney *U* test revealed statistically significant differences in both the minimum and maximum duration of immobility ($p = 0.02$), as well as a trend toward significance for total activity duration ($p = 0.083$). The mean values support these findings: mice treated with 250 mg/kg exhibited a longer total duration of activity (182.06 vs. 137.74 in controls) and shorter and less frequent immobility episodes (57.79 vs. 102.12) (Table 1). The results were expressed in seconds (s). Administration of the substance at a dose of 250 mg/kg resulted in increased active escape behavior accompanied by a reduction in immobility time. These findings may indicate enhanced behavioral activation and suggest a potential stimulatory or antidepressant-like effect of the substance at this dose. When comparing the control group with the group receiving the higher dose of the substance (500 mg/kg), a statistically significant difference was observed for the minimum duration of the active state. In the control group (0.87 ± 0.17), the minimum duration was significantly higher than in the group treated with 500 mg/kg (0.38 ± 0.33),

with this effect reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.026$). This indicates that treatment with the higher dose affects the minimum duration of active periods, altering the pattern of activity expression in the animals. A trend toward a difference was also observed for the mean duration of the active state, with longer average active periods in the control group (8.25 ± 2.87) compared to mice receiving 500 mg/kg (5.48 ± 0.64). This difference was marginally statistically significant ($p = 0.050$), suggesting a possible dose-dependent effect on behavior. No statistically significant differences were found between the two groups for the remaining parameters, including both active and inactive states ($p > 0.05$).

For the parameter minimum duration of the inactive state (time during which mice were not active or not swimming), a substantial difference was observed between the negative control group and the group receiving 1000 mg/kg of the substance. The mean value in the control group was 0.42 ± 0.08 s, whereas in the experimental group it was significantly lower at 0.17 ± 0.09 s. The results of the nonparametric Mann–Whitney *U* test demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.014$). This suggests that at the highest dose of 1000 mg/kg, the animals spent significantly less time in an inactive state, which may be interpreted as increased activity or a stimulatory effect of the substance on behavior. When comparing the negative control group (treated with physiological saline) and the group receiving 1000 mg/kg of the tested substance on the fifth day, statistically significant differences were observed in both the minimum duration of activity ($p = 0.019$) and the minimum duration of immobility ($p = 0.020$). Animals treated with 1000 mg/kg exhibited significantly shorter active and inactive episodes compared with the control group. The mean values support these findings: the minimum duration of activity was lower in the treated animals (0.26 ± 0.27) than in the controls (0.87 ± 0.17), and the minimum duration of immobility was also reduced (0.17 ± 0.09 vs. 0.42 ± 0.09). At the same time, the mean duration of immobility episodes was higher in the 1000 mg/kg group (5.79 ± 2.78) compared with the control group (3.45 ± 1.41), suggesting greater variability in swimming and an alternation of short active phases with longer periods of rest. These results may be interpreted as evidence of a dose-dependent effect of the substance, whereby higher doses induce alterations in escape behavior and overall

Table 1. Effects compared with the negative control after 5 days.

Groups	Total periods (s)		Average duration (s)		Min duration (s)		Max duration (s)		Total periods (s)		Average duration (s)		Min duration (s)		Max duration (s)	
	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive	Active	Inactive
Negative	20.40 ± 3.05	137.74 ± 40.32**^	8.25 ± 2.87***^	0.87 ± 0.16***^	29.19 ± 22.31	20.00 ± 3.16	102.12 ± 40.30**^	5.04 ± 2.41***^	0.42 ± 0.07**	22.49 ± 5.37**						
250 mg/kg	21.40 ± 7.77	182.06 ± 24.82**^	9.10 ± 4.11	0.37 ± 0.45	49.45 ± 22.81	20.40 ± 7.54	57.79 ± 24.81**^	2.66 ± 0.62***^	0.13 ± 0.09***^	9.98 ± 3.80**^						
500 mg/kg	22.60 ± 5.03	124.83 ± 32.20**	5.48 ± 0.64***	0.38 ± 0.33***	27.95 ± 20.19	22.20 ± 4.87	115.04 ± 32.18**	5.72 ± 3.25**	0.35 ± 0.20	25.17 ± 11.81**						
1000 mg/kg	17.40 ± 8.65	145.76 ± 64.78	20.42 ± 32.46	0.25 ± 0.27***^	56.97 ± 77.52	17.00 ± 8.92	94.10 ± 64.77	5.79 ± 2.77***^	0.16 ± 0.09***^	18.89 ± 12.55***						
Positive	17.80 ± 13.90	194.14 ± 42.86**	60.80 ± 101.56	48.84 ± 106.79	97.25 ± 103.03	16.80 ± 13.90	45.73 ± 42.88**	2.12 ± 1.44**	0.34 ± 0.25	6.22 ± 5.30**						

** Statistically significant difference between non-treated groups and groups treated with 250 mg/kg; $p < 0.05$.

*** Statistically significant difference between non-treated groups and groups treated with 500 mg/kg; $p \leq 0.05$.

**** Statistically significant difference between non-treated groups and groups treated with 1000 mg/kg; $p < 0.05$.

^ n = 4.

behavioral patterns. After ten days of treatment, no statistically significant differences were observed when compared to the negative control group.

Effects compared with the positive control treated with imipramine

After 5 days

When comparing the positive control group (treated with an antidepressant) and the group receiving 500 mg/kg of the substance, statistically significant differences were observed across several parameters. Regarding total activity duration, the 500 mg/kg group exhibited significantly lower values (124.83 ± 32.20) compared with the positive control (194.14 ± 42.87), with the difference reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.032$). In addition, significant differences were detected for both total immobility duration and maximum duration of an inactive episode ($p = 0.032$; $p = 0.008$). Animals treated with 500 mg/kg spent significantly more time in an inactive state (115.04 ± 32.18) and exhibited longer inactive episodes (25.17 ± 11.82) than those in the positive control group (45.73 ± 42.88 ; 6.22 ± 5.30 , respectively) (Table 2). These findings indicate that at a dose of 500 mg/kg, the substance suppresses active swimming activity and increases immobility periods compared with the antidepressant, suggesting a potential sedative or depressant effect on animal behavior.

When comparing the positive control group (treated with an antidepressant) and the group receiving 1000 mg/kg of the substance on the fifth day, statistically significant differences were observed for some of the examined parameters. The Mann–Whitney U test revealed a significant difference in mean immobility duration ($p = 0.028$), with animals treated with 1000 mg/kg exhibiting longer inactive periods than those in the positive control group. The mean duration of immobility was higher in the 1000 mg/kg group (5.11 ± 2.85) compared with the positive control (2.12 ± 1.45) (Table 2).

A trend toward a difference was also noted for the maximum duration of immobility ($p = 0.076$), with higher values observed in the 1000 mg/kg group (18.89 ± 12.55) relative to the positive control (6.22 ± 5.30) (Table 2). These results suggest that at a dose of 1000 mg/kg, the substance may induce longer periods of floating, indicating suppression of the active escape response compared with the antidepressant.

After 10 days

When comparing the positive control group (antidepressant-treated) with the group receiving 500 mg/kg of the substance on the tenth day, statistically significant differences were observed across several parameters. According to the Mann–Whitney U test, a significant difference was found in total activity duration ($p = 0.016$), with animals treated with 500 mg/kg exhibiting significantly lower activity levels (85.97 ± 41.69) compared with the positive control group (194.14 ± 42.87). Significant differences were also observed for total immobility duration

($p = 0.016$) and maximum duration of immobility ($p = 0.009$). At a dose of 500 mg/kg, these values were higher (153.89 ± 41.70 and 37.39 ± 19.79 , respectively) than those recorded for the positive control group (45.73 ± 42.88 and 6.22 ± 5.30). The difference in mean duration of immobility was likewise statistically significant ($p = 0.009$), with higher values observed in the 500 mg/kg group (10.92 ± 4.61) compared with the control group (2.12 ± 1.45) (Table 3). A trend toward a difference was noted for the minimum duration of activity ($p = 0.052$) and the maximum duration of activity ($p = 0.076$), with lower values observed in the treated group. These findings indicate that at a dose of 500 mg/kg, the substance markedly suppresses active behavior and increases immobility time compared with animals treated with an antidepressant.

When comparing the positive control group (antidepressant-treated) with the group receiving 1000 mg/kg of the substance on the tenth day, statistically significant differences were likewise observed across several parameters. Total activity duration was significantly lower in the 1000 mg/kg group (82.73 ± 82.71) compared with the positive control group (194.14 ± 42.87 ; $p = 0.047$). A similar trend was observed for the mean duration of activity ($p = 0.047$) and the minimum duration of activity ($p = 0.085$), with lower values recorded in the treated group. Immobility time was also increased at the 1000 mg/kg dose: total immobility duration was higher (157.12 ± 82.70) than in the positive control group (45.73 ± 42.88 ; $p = 0.047$), as was the maximum duration of immobility (34.32 ± 21.59 vs. 6.22 ± 5.30 ; $p = 0.047$). The mean duration of immobility was likewise higher in treated animals (11.13 ± 6.55) compared with the positive control group (2.12 ± 1.45 ; $p = 0.076$) (Table 3). These results demonstrate that at a dose of 1000 mg/kg, the substance strongly suppresses active swimming periods and increases immobility time relative to animals treated with an antidepressant.

Effects compared between the doses of 5- and 10-day treatment

Doses of 250 mg/kg bw/day

Comparing 5-day treatment and 10-day treatment with the lower dose, no statistically significant differences were observed in most parameters for the groups that received 250 mg/kg for 5 days and for 10 days ($p > 0.05$), with the exception of the minimum duration of immobility, which was significantly longer on day 10 ($p = 0.016$). This indicates that with prolonged administration of the 250 mg/kg dose, an increase in the minimum periods of immobility is observed, while the other activity parameters remain similar.

Doses of 500 mg/kg bw/day

Comparing the groups receiving 500 mg/kg for 5 days and 10 days, significant differences were observed in the total number of active periods and the total number of inactive periods ($p = 0.028$), with mice on day 5 showing

Table 2. Effects compared with the positive control treated with imipramine after 5 days.

Groups	Total periods (s)	Total duration (s)	Average duration (s)	Min duration (s)	Max duration (s)	Total periods (s)	Total duration (s)	Average duration (s)	Min duration (s)	Max duration (s)
	Active					Inactive				
Negative	20.40 ± 3.05	151.49 ± 46.53	7.60 ± 2.89	0.70 ± 0.40	29.19 ± 22.31	20.00 ± 3.16	88.37 ± 46.51	4.43 ± 2.50	0.42 ± 0.08	19.73 ± 7.73
250 mg/kg	21.40 ± 7.77	172.68 ± 30.04	9.10 ± 4.11	0.37 ± 0.45	49.45 ± 22.81	20.40 ± 7.54	67.18 ± 30.04	3.63 ± 2.22	0.19 ± 0.14	18.09 ± 18.45
500 mg/kg	22.60 ± 5.03	124.83 ± 32.20 **	5.48 ± 0.64	0.38 ± 0.33	27.95 ± 20.19	22.20 ± 4.87	115.04 ± 32.18 **	5.72 ± 3.25 **	0.35 ± 0.20	25.17 ± 11.81 **
1000 mg/kg	17.40 ± 8.65	145.76 ± 64.78	20.42 ± 32.46	2.52 ± 5.06	56.97 ± 77.52	17.00 ± 8.92	94.10 ± 64.77	5.11 ± 2.84 ***	0.31 ± 0.33	18.89 ± 12.55 ***
Positive	17.80 ± 13.90	194.14 ± 42.86 **	60.80 ± 101.56	48.84 ± 106.79	97.25 ± 103.03	16.80 ± 13.90	45.73 ± 42.88 **	2.12 ± 1.44 **	0.34 ± 0.25	6.22 ± 5.30 **

** Statistically significant difference between positive control group and group treated with 500 mg/kg; $p \leq 0.05$.

*** Statistically significant difference between positive control group and group treated with 1000 mg/kg; $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Effects compared with the positive control treated with imipramine after 10 days.

Groups	Total periods (s)	Total duration (s)	Average duration (s)	Min duration (s)	Max duration (s)	Total periods (s)	Total duration (s)	Average duration (s)	Min duration (s)	Max duration (s)
	Active					Inactive				
Negative	20.40 ± 3.05	151.49 ± 46.53	7.60 ± 2.89	0.70 ± 0.40	29.19 ± 22.31	20.00 ± 3.16	88.37 ± 46.51	4.43 ± 2.50	0.42 ± 0.08	19.73 ± 7.73
250 mg/kg	22.60 ± 7.73	131.77 ± 68.87	7.14 ± 6.62	0.32 ± 0.45	34.49 ± 37.17	21.80 ± 7.66	108.09 ± 68.87	4.90 ± 3.32	0.56 ± 0.27	21.55 ± 23.38
500 mg/kg	15.20 ± 3.27	85.93 ± 41.69 **	5.67 ± 2.84	0.07 ± 0.06 **	21.65 ± 19.99 **	14.80 ± 3.11	153.89 ± 41.69 **	10.92 ± 4.61 **	0.75 ± 0.58	37.38 ± 19.79 **
1000 mg/kg	14.60 ± 5.64	82.73 ± 82.70 ***	7.37 ± 10.02 ***	0.21 ± 0.34 ***	21.75 ± 32.98 ***	14.00 ± 5.52	157.12 ± 82.69 ***	11.13 ± 6.54 ***	1.22 ± 1.15	34.32 ± 21.58 ***
Positive	17.80 ± 13.90	194.14 ± 42.86 **	60.88 ± 101.55 ***	48.84 ± 106.79 **	97.25 ± 103.03**	16.80 ± 13.90	45.73 ± 42.88 **	2.12 ± 1.44 **	0.34 ± 0.25	6.22 ± 5.30 **

** Statistically significant difference between positive control group and group treated with 500 mg/kg; $p \leq 0.05$.

*** Statistically significant difference between positive control group and group treated with 1000 mg/kg; $p < 0.05$.

more active periods and more inactive periods compared to day 10 (more dynamic periods were observed). The other parameters, including the average duration of activity and the minimum and maximum durations, did not differ statistically significantly ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the duration of the 500 mg/kg treatment primarily affects the number of active and inactive periods, while the duration of individual periods remains relatively stable. It is also noteworthy that the mean duration of inactive periods increased on day 10 ($M = 10.92 \pm 4.61$ s) compared to day 5 ($M = 5.72 \pm 3.26$ s).

Doses of 1000 mg/kg bw/day

The comparison between 1000 mg/kg bw for 5 days and 1000 mg/kg bw for 10 days showed no statistically significant differences in most parameters ($p > 0.05$), including the total number of active periods and the total duration of activity. However, a trend toward a longer maximum duration of active periods was observed on day 5 (56.97 ± 77.52) compared to day 10 (21.75 ± 32.98), as well as a shorter minimum duration of inactive periods on day 5 (0.31 ± 0.33) compared to day 10 (1.22 ± 1.15), suggesting that the duration of administration may influence the variability of active and inactive periods, although these differences do not reach statistical significance.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that *C. reticulata* extract exhibits moderate antidepressant-like activity, particularly at a dose of 250 mg/kg following short-term administration. No statistically significant difference was observed between the total duration of activity on the 10th day at doses of 500 mg/kg and 1000 mg/kg. The observed effects are characterized by reduced immobility and

increased behavioral activity in experimental mice. However, the lack of consistent effects at higher doses and after prolonged treatment suggests a complex dose-response relationship. Additional studies are needed on the different fractions of the extract to determine the most active one, to clarify the pharmacological effect and mechanisms of action of the extract of *C. reticulata*, including its effects on active escape response and sedation, and to evaluate long-term safety and efficacy.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Orlando Ortiz for his valuable assistance in the collection and taxonomic identification of the plant material of *Cecropia reticulata*. The authors express their gratitude to Technology Valley (www.technology-valley.com) for providing the high-precision Computer Vision framework that enabled the autonomous, non-invasive tracking of behavioral phenotypes with impressive accuracy and data integrity. In this study, the Council of Medical Science at the Medical University of Sofia under Contract No. D-223/04.06.2025 is acknowledged.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: All performed procedures were approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (449/10.10.2025).

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: Vision Engine.

Used for: Data analysis, Software and automation.

Funding

This study was financed by the European Union-NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of

the Republic of Bulgaria, project BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01, "Strategic research and innovation program for development of Medical University – Sofia".

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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